

Inventory Management through Lean Logistics and Warehousing Techniques

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Abstract

Inventory is one of the eight deadly wastes in Lean. It is caused by overproduction (producing more than is immediately needed) but in turn it causes several other wastes. How does excess inventory manifest itself? I.e. Extra space, Extra people, waste conveyance, extra costs. Inventory management in lean is built around the same principles that govern most lean activity: create a simple set of tools that can be used directly in the workplace that will help surface problems so that they can be addressed. Inventory management is thus quite different in lean, starting with the view of inventory as a waste rather than an asset. From a practical point of view, what this means is that inventory reduction is built into the fabric of the system, just like it is for any other waste. Because of this, they are typically no special efforts or programs aimed at reducing excess inventory. Reducing inventory is a part of everyday work life. In this paper we will cover two important topics for the supply chain, warehousing and logistics. We will cover the traditional view of physical control of inventories, then the relationships between the warehouse and the organization and then we review traditional logistics activities. In second half of this research paper we will review distribution requirements planning, Lean warehousing and Lean logistics.

Keywords: Lean logistics, Inventory management, waste, distribution

Literature Review

So what does green Lean/ resource management have to do with risk management? If you think about it, a lot more than meets the eye. Risk management, specifically within the supply, is a process of identifying items within the supply chain that could cause problems. Granted, this is a pretty broad statement, so we will try to break it down so it makes sense and can be used to actually manage risks

As we mentioned in the our report, risk management is full of challenges, mostly because of two extremes: either nothing is done, or it is made so complicated it either can't be done or the users get caught up in the complexity. In most cases, people just really don't know what to do. So, where to begin? Again, your value stream map is a great source documented for risk management. In doing this, another similar template will be used, but this time, it will be used throughout the map, not just in work centers.

Looking at what is needed to do some basic risk management, the resource template is a good starting point. It provides some of the information needed to assess risk, but we need to look at in a different way. We are going to continue to look at resources, but we are going to expand this list to cover additional resources. Also, we are not concerned with output, but rather a high level risk assessment. Table below shows a risk management template. This risk assessment is to provide a framework to identify risk items that should be addressed. We have purposely avoided assigning probabilities, point values, etc., that often get people wrapped up in preparing the process but often failing to act- what we like to call getting ready to get ready. Risk management in this framework provides a list of items that can be prioritized and then worked on. For example, you may identify a commodity in your product that appears to be headed for a shortage position, that will make it tougher to get and more expensive. Your choice is to live with this or do something. The "do something" can be a lot of things: start forward

buying to alleviate some of the shortages price increases , or examining if you replace that commodity with something else, or at least

exploring the possibility. We hope these templates will help you to talk / fret about these topics less , and actually do something.

Resources	Risk Factors
Transportation	Outbound Transits Suppliers risk-availability , cost trends, health of transportation markets
Commodity	Item/Commodity risk-market cost and availability trends
Supplier	Supplier risk-number of suppliers, market health, location of supplier, in outbound transport risks, tier-related risks- suppliers and commodity
Market	Customer/market risk-dependence , health of product line , competition , price trends
Waste	Waste risks-availability of service , price of disposal , recycling and/or emissions real/potential costs, hazardous material issues - handling and handling cost trends
Labor	Availability of skilled employees, specific skills-internal and external (suppliers, tiers) and cost of labor trends
Assets	Age of equipment systems, availability of service parts and technicians systems still supported?
Utilities	Cost and availability trends

Research Methodology

Strategic Development of Lean logistics

There is no question that lean will contribute positively to logistics an supply chain activities. The challenges are to understand how to leverage the value of Lean in Logistics. Lean principles ca n sometimes is counterintuitive, making it difficult for operations people to embrace the value proposition. For Example, a transportation manager will struggle with the concept of increasing frequency of deliveries if personal performance is measured on transportation costs. Hence, lean logistics can be implemented successfully; it must be a cooperative initiative. This is not to say that a company must be a lean organization prior to implementing Lean in the logistics function.

The important lesson is that Lean teaches us sound business principles. Lean is not a trend, fad or flavor of the month. They are well packaged set of business excellence principles and tools. The trick is to unwrap the package and choose the principles and tools that are

needed and best suit your particular situation. By using those principles and tools, an organization can design a business excellence model that will fit the culture and goals of the company.

The Two Perspectives of Lean Logistics

Lean Logistics # 1

The inbound logistics function supporting a lean manufacturing facility.

Lean Logistics # 2

Logistics activities where the overall operational strategy is based on Lean principles and tools. This can include transportation, warehousing, order management, material handling an inventory control.

With these two definitions in mind, it becomes apparent that lean logistics has the potential to become a confusing and complicated model. The goal then is to simplify the complicated. That is what we have attempted to accomplish in this project. Reviewing and analyzing all lean and

six sigma with the logistics function. Our goal is to arm the logistics professional with the knowledge required to reduce waste, manage inventories, and create more effective processes.

significant initiative. We all need to be on the same page! This is especially very true for the logistics function , where a cooperate global logistics strategy may not exist.

The Importance of Logistics Bridge Model

The use of a model allows an organization to talk a common language, the first step to any

Any model that spotlights on results will be multidimensional. With logistics span Model , the measurements depend on the progressive system of a normal association. The model takes a gander at logistics from the perspective of CEO first then penetrates down to the vital level and in conclusion depicts the strategic regions for effective usage. This methodology takes after

Lean tenet by making a model that can be comprehended by all levels of the association. By taking after the model , the CEO will realize what will be expert , as will the senior administration and cutting edge supervisors. The Logistics span model gives a participate methodology that can be utilized to execute a world class incline logistics framework.

The Inventory Holding Cost

Stock conveying cost determination is the possibility of doing as such as often as possible. Stock conveying expense ought to be alert, as dynamic as an organization's business open

doors. As an organization's normal rate of profit for new speculations advances, so excessively should the stock conveying cost rate. The rate decided at one point in time ought not be held in

such respect that it can't be addressed over the time and returned to. Stock conveying expense is not liable to change significantly inside the course of year , yet ought to dependably mirror the truth of the organization's changing cost conditions and venture open doors.

When you have a superior handle on what it is truly costing you to hold stock, interest ought to swing to how deals can be augmented with minimal measure of stock. Every single other thing being equivalent , you ought to attempt to

cover request by requesting littler amounts all the more much of the time from your supply sources., along these lines accomplishing more stock turns. "Inventory turns" alludes to the quantities of times every year that normal stock offers. The quantity of turns is normally decided in view of the estimation of normal stock and the business volume at cost, communicated scientifically as

$$\text{Inventory turns} = \frac{\text{Sales volume at cost}}{\text{value of average inventory}}$$

SIX SIGMA AND LOGISTICAN

The possibility of distinction diminishing is first to logistician. As communicated, logistics is about regulating stock, directing stock is about administering change. In case we look at different sorts of stock, we will plainly see why assortment accept such an essential part by the way we manage inventories all through the business and store system.

For example, prosperity or bolster stocks are inventories that we need to fence against inquiries (i.e, the assortments from the standard). That is, we keep up security

stocks because of assortments in supplier quality, transportation trustworthiness, creating process limit , and the customer demand outlines. In a manner of speaking, whether we can fathom and control assortments in our methodology from the suppliers to customers, then we will have the ability to reduce our reliance on the backings radically. In such way, logistician need to see themselves as analysts like the people who make rates for mischance security. Analysts look at key variables the time of drivers, sexual introduction of the drivers, sorts of vehicles driven, measures of past behavior (eg speeding tickets and

mishaps) and thereafter they choose security rates that mirrors the variability in the data this is essentially why the sixteen year old male who drive sports auto will have the most raised assurance rate.

LEAN AND LOGISTICIAN

The effect of incline toward the logistician is noteworthy. A typical confusion of the incline reasoning is that it just discovers application in assembling settings. The objective of incline is to wipe out waste and diminishing work in procedure inventories and thusly, diminish process and assembling lead times, at last expanding store network speed and stream. Incline additionally have a key social components to it that is pivotal to the logistician, the idea of " aggregate expense" . The incline specialist does not concentrate on individual cost components, for example, transportation or warehousing , yet rather concentrates on aggregate expense. With stock conveying cost speaking to 15 to 40 percent of aggregate logistics costs for some ventures , settling on choices taking into account complete expense has emotional ramifications for the logisticians. Sadly however, numerous associations never grasp the aggregate cost idea completely, as poor choices are made ceaselessly in light of customarily noticeable cost drivers like transportation , warehousing and per unit buy costs.

STRATEGY AND PLANNING TOOL

Lean and six sigma are designed to be comprehensive programs . Embedded within two initiative are pervasive philosophical principles, values , models and tools. This creates a challenges when trying to describe lean and six sigma have to offer when combine. As well it can make training and implementation challenging because employees may get confused between theory and practical next steps.

Lean and Six Sigma across four categories

- 1- Strategy and planning
- 2- Problem Solving
- 3- Operations
- 4- Measurements

VOICE OF THE CUSTOMERS

When it comes to logistics services it is easy to see that all the customers want the same services or expected the same level of service some customer see value added services like labeling an packaging , and other call for transportation and storage and still others seek transportation. Among those calling form transportation services , one customer may expect 95% on time performance ,98% for another and 100% for yet another. Clearly , a uniform approach design and fulfillment will not accommodate customer diverse needs.

Key expects of the customer the supplier must understand include answers to the following questions

- 1- What are the goals of customers?
- 2- What are the motivating forces behind these goals?
- 3- What are the customer's challenges constraints and resources ?
- 4- How can we help the customer meet these goals, given the challenges ?

PACKAGING AS VISUAL CONTROL

Today numerous assembling operations in North America are for all intents and purposes free of nonessential bundling. However , the infrequent shipments can appear at these plants in the old standard, folded box . The presence of the creased

bundling serves as a vital message that something is amiss in the framework.

One of the three conceivable things has happened

1-The supplier has obtain excessively couple of compartments, making it impossible to handle the require the volume at the plant.

2-The returnable holder has neglected to advance back to the legitimate supplier that requirements totes for ensuing use

3-The supplier has fabricate parts ahead of time of the need , out dividing kanban the interest for the parts

.ORDER TRANSMISSION

Ordinary Methods of correspondence can make a request transmission and tedious stage all together cycle. Take , for the occasion, a request transmitting via telephone between the clients acquiring operator and supplier client administration

THE SIMPOC MODEL

To answer the question " What does a standardize process look like ? "we need to break down the process itself. The good news is that all processes are made of the same basic variables. The SIMPOC (Supplier- Inputs-Measurement-Procedure-Outputs-Customers) model defines the key variables and provides a framework for documenting standardize processes by answering the following questions

1-**Supplier** :Who supplies the inputs for the process.

delegate. The buying specialist should first discover the chance to start the call at time at which somebody is liable to be at the flip side to acknowledge it. While most real organizations give every minute of every day/365 client administration accessibility, it stays a long way from all inclusive. Thus , the call may restricted to the cover in the hours of operation for both client and supplier. A client on the US east drift may to defer an early morning call until the west drift the supplier is open for business.

Electronic methods of correspondences have made request transmission for all intents and purposes case . Electronic information exchange EDI has been hailed over the previous decades for its capacity to facilitated between the client's PC and supplier's PC without human intercession and the blunder the variability inborn in human movement in addition to , EDI frameworks are the not totally shape interruptions

2- **Inputs** : What are the inputs for the process? This may include material, people or information.

3-**Measurement** : How do we measure the purpose to ensure the success?

4- **Procedure** : What are the procedures for the process? This includes documenting the process steps and timings of each step.

5-**Outputs**-What are the expected outputs of the process? These can include actual products, information, or documentation.

6- **Customers**- Who are the customers of the process and what they do they expect ?

The SIMPOC is a valuable---- tool to compare the current condition of processes and to develop standardize operations.

Mondelez Process : Receiving Function of Two Divisional Manufacturing Facilities

SIMPOC- Receiving Function	Plant 1	Plant 2
Supplier to process	Ordering Department	Purchasing
Input for the process	Receiving Schedule	ASNs
Measurements	Receiving Time	none
Procedures	Documented	None
Outputs	Part to Line side	Parts to stores
Customers	Line Side	Stores Area

This high level of process of a SIMPOC shows how the tool can be used to compare processes in different facilities. Clearly, these two plants have a very different processes in place to receive material.

If we can document the SIMPOC for each process in our operations, the result will be a set of documented standard operations. Once this accomplished , the standard is set as noted , a standardize , documented process is one that new team members can quickly understand and contribute to immediately. Even though a process become standardize , however , we should not become content with it. The vision is always seek new , better ways to perform the work

Traditional Physical Control of Inventories

Let's start the warehousing portion of the session with discussing what warehousing is all about. In basic terms , it is all about the physical control of inventories , typically finished goods inventories. One major tool that typically has been used to help maintain this control is ABC. The ABC principle states that effort and money

can be saved by applying looser controls to low - dollar-volume class items than the high -dollar-volume class items.

Methodology ABC Classification

The characterization of a gathering of things in diminishing request of yearly dollar volume (cost increased by anticipated volume) or other criteria. This cluster is then part into three classes, called A, B and C. The A gathering for the most part speaks to 10% to 20% by number of things and half to 70% by anticipated dollar volume. The following gathering , B, normally speaks to around 20% of the things and around 20% of the dollar volume. The class C contains 60% to 70% of the things and speaks to around 10% to 30% of the dollar volume. The ABC rule expresses that exertion and cash can be spared through applying looser controls to low - dollar-volume class things than will be connected to high - dollar - volume class things. The ABC rule is appropriate to inventories , buying , deals, et cetera.

ABC has been broadly utilized and is extraordinary device to organize how stock is dealt with; certain SKUs in the stockroom are more vital than different things. As beforehand specified, ABC investigation is utilized to oversee inventories in distribution center. This normally done by utilizing the ABC to set up cycle numbering cycles, with A sections being tallied more as often as possible than C parts; the A sections are obviously more vital than C parts. Despite the fact that this is valid on a general level, care must be taken not to disregard the B and C things, the absence of C things can close you down pretty much as fast as an A thing would.

Moreover, numerous stockrooms use ABC to set up physical stock areas, with A sections being set up either near the delivery zone (front of distribution center) of basically in the brilliant zone-rack range ordinarily at a physical case of this Figure beneath

FMEA AND LOGISTICS SKILLS

Logistics is the cornerstone to store network administration achievement. It is not about transportation or warehousing; The logistics center is :The development of item : This is more than transportation of products. the modes and bearers chose must supplement the production network methodology and must be receptive to the requirements of clients and whole chain.

The development of data : Information innovation is vital to being responsive. It must be both inward the endeavor - and outside, with clients and suppliers

Fetches: This is the expense of the whole inventory network, both working and capital. It is not only the expense of discrete cost variables, for example, cargo or warehousing.

Time/Service: Supply fasten administration is customized to and receptive to every client. To pick up an upper hand, administration and time

pressure are key to keep clients recharged and inventories under control.

Combination :The joining of framework and individuals, collaboration, must be both inside and outer. On the off chance that it is not, then there are holes, potential for postponements and blunders and disappointments in the store network process

DISTRIBUTION REQUIREMENTS PLANNING -DRP

1-The capacity of deciding the need to renew stock at branch stockrooms. A period - staged request point methodology is utilized where the arranged requests at the branch distribution center level are "detonated" by means of MRP rationale to end up gross prerequisites on the supplying source. On account of multilevel dispersion systems, this blast procedure can proceed down through the different levels of provincial distribution centers (expert stockroom, manufacturing plant stockroom, and so on) and get to be contribution to the expert generation plan. Request on the supplying sources is perceived as reliant, and standard MRP rationale applies.

2-More by and large, recharging stock computation, which might be founded on other arranging methodologies, for example, period request amounts or supplant precisely what was utilized, as opposed to being constrained to the time staged request point approach.

LEAN WAREHOUSING

First, we are going to talk about Lean warehousing and how it builds on some of the best practices that many warehouse people already do. Although the setting of inventory levels is an important part of warehousing, we

have already know that subject , so we are going to assume that the inventory levels are proper. So , what are some of the key items , other than inventory, that are important to manage in the

warehouse. Note that not all the items that need to be controlled are critical ; this list can be viewed as the major cost drivers in the warehouses.

Example of DRP mechanics

Warehouse A	Week							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Gross Requirements	80	80	80	70	80	90	90	90
Schedule receipts								
Project on hand 90	10	30	50	80	0	10	20	30
PLO receipts		100	100	100		100	100	100
PLO releases	100	100	100		100	100	100	

Warehouse B	Week							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Gross Requirements	30	30	30	20	20	30	90	35
Schedule receipts								
Project on hand 90	60	30	0	30	0	15	30	45
PLO receipts				50	50	50	50	
PLO releases		50		50	50	50		

Warehouse C	Week							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Gross Requirements	60	60	70	70	80	80	90	90
Schedule receipts								
Project on hand 170	11	50	80	80	10	30	50	60
PLO receipts			100	100	100	100		100
PLO releases	100		100	100	100	100		

Central Supply	Week							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Gross Requirements	200	150	200	150	250	250	100	0
Schedule receipts								
Project on hand 170	350	200	0	150	200	200	250	150
PLO receipts				300	300	300		
PLO releases		300	300	300				

	Quality	Lead Time
Warehouse A	100	1
Warehouse B	50	2
Warehouse C	100	2
Central Supply	300	2

Inventory

There is no doubt that this is cost driver 1, but we have discussed how inventory levels are set. A warehouse is just another "supermarket" where goods are held for sale, and you only have a supermarket if you cannot match when and where customers want product with your ability to supply the goods on a timely basis. In most cases, shipping lead time is a normal expectation for customers, so you also have to consider the additional manufacturing or supply time. Can you deliver product to the customers at or under the lead time that they expect? If customers expect immediate or near-immediate order fulfillment, then you may need one or more warehouses. The process for identifying where these need to be located is not changed in Lean. However, how much inventory is held will be calculated by the same rules we discussed in determining supermarket size.

Space

Typically warehouse space is assigned on a square foot basis and is probably cost driver 3. Many organizations find themselves with too little space, given that space is used inefficiently and growth is usually not planned for symptoms of this are leased trailers or outside/off-site warehouse space.

Labor

This is cost driver 2 and, as we will discuss, is probably the least controlled

Lean warehousing looks at space use as being a critical issue to deal with. Space usage is commonly referred to as slotting, but it goes beyond the concept of where items are placed within the warehouse; it also takes into consideration how much inventory is put into the location and attempts to create a handful of standard location sizes.

Slotting is a simple concept: put higher velocity items closer to point of use, then slower velocity items. The reason to do slotting is that it can do more to save labor cost than just about anything else. How? By reducing the travel time-walking or driving in the warehouse. If your faster moving items are closer to their point of use either receipt or shipping, then people will be traveling less to put away or pick these items. One of the biggest issues is in how to do slotting. Some people think that slotting can only be done with a warehouse management system, but most warehouse management systems, especially those included as standard in most ERP systems, generally available do not do slotting.

Example :

The example is an excerpt from a monthly turns report that has been edited (Note : The turns are totally fictitious). The key here is that we are looking at year to date (YTD) issues. Make sure you have at least six months of data, which should be enough to be representative sample unless the majority of your items are short term or seasonal type items. If that is the case , you may want to set up two slotting areas : one for seasonal items and other for non seasonal. As you can see , the excerpt has a wide range of YTD issues quantities

The next step is to simply sort descending , on the YTD column. This can guide you on where to slot. Next , add a slot column to help. The slot column is where you will fill in where you plan to put that item. This requires that you have a logical warehouse location system. This is typically done with a mix of alphanumeric characters that represents

- Aisle
- Rack
- Shelf
- Bin

Slotting in Excel starts with gathering data

SKU	Description	Current Inventory	YTD Issues	Turns	Days Lead Time	Last Year's Sales Unit
30-5681T	A	187	2073	11.085	1	9
73-1650	B	108	194	1.796		416
CAW-23	C	83	194	2.337	1	2062
E-59X	D	11520	6912	0..600	120	0
LABEL-2	E	48144	7056	0.146	1	4911
LAM-182	F	417739	445261	1.065	1	3249541
M20G	G	2079	7003	3.368	1	25090
MDF12-68A	H	45	194	4.311		123
PEN-WH	I	3622	2069	0.571	1	14079
PS-43	J	107	2046	19.121		18
TUBING-6	K	6300	337000	5.349	1	960800
VPF-19	L	436100	316300	0.725	1	4013883

The next step is simply sort descending on the YTD column. This can guide you on where to slot

SKU	Description	Current Inventory	YTD Issues	Turns	Days Lead Time	Last Year's Sales Unit	Slot
LAM-182	F	417739	445231	1.065	1	3249541	
TUBING-6	K	63000	337000	5.349	1	960800	
VPF-19	L	436100	316300	0.725	1	4013883	
LABEL-2	E	48144	7056	0.146	1	4911	
M20G	G	2079	7003	3.368	1	25090	
E-59X	D	11520	6912	0.6	120	0	
W-184F	M	2640	6888	2.6609	100	120	
30-5681T	A	187	2073	11.085	1	9	
PEN-WH	I	3622	2069	0.571	1	14079	
PS-43	J	107	2046	191.21		18	
73-1650	B	108	194	1.796		416	
CAW-23	C	83	194	2.337	1	2062	
MDF12-68A	H	45	194	4.311		123	

CONCLUSION

In this research we have reviewed the details about managing inventory through lean logistics and warehousing approach that means waste less supply logistics network. lean logistics covers a pretty broad number of items, and we will cover these during the remainder of the research. Lean logistics is the application of Lean principles within the logistics part of the supply chain to help optimize the entire supply chain.

As with the other areas that we have covered in this research, there is an emphasis on ensuring that the process is robust and capable, the idea being that people will generally not make mistakes unless the process allows them to. This is just one example where Lean has taken a core concept respect for people in this case and applied it to a specific area, in this case quality control and improvement, with the result being a

new approach that has strengths from the traditional approach as well as a new strengths from the core value. Lean is a complete operating system, and needs to be approached and adopted as such, not just as a set of loosely connected tools created to eliminate waste.

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